

ROLE OF AGE IN INVESTMENT DECISIONS

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ABSTRACT

Individuals project various biases in their investment decisions. It may vary from emotional to cognitive biases. Amongst many demographic factors age is analyzed in the present study. The objective is to observe influence of age on behavioral biases which later will affect investment decision. Investors across various cities of India were selected as sample respondents. Data was collected using structured questionnaire. The study applied chi-square and kruskal wallis test to analyze the influence of age on decisions like expected return, portfolio size, investment objective, investment avenues etc. The study concluded that investors across various age groups vary in their investment decisions. Decisions are affected by cognitive ability of an individual and risk tolerance level. Also responsibilities, capital base and income levels vary across various age categories. All these forces play a crucial role in financial decision making.

Key words: Age, behavioral biase, investment decision, chi square, demographics

1 INTRODUCTION

Individuals often have to take certain decisions. These decisions may be big or small. Some decisions are easy and straight forward while others are complicated and require detailed analysis and multi-step approach to make a decision. An area of study known as “cognitive psychology” can be referred to understand how people make a choice. What factors influences their decisions and several heuristics in the process of decision making.

Decisions are integral part of everyone’s life. The process of making a decision is a complex mechanism of human thinking. It involves a structural procedure and gets affected by various factors and course of action. Some individual differences may also affect the decision. Age is one of such difference that is being long studied in various disciplines. Evidence suggests that age declines an individual’s cognitive abilities. Working memory, speed of processing and executive functioning begins to decline in mid-20s and advances into 70s. The three strategies used by individuals while taking a decision as identified by researchers are cognitive, heuristics and biases. The use of these strategies also gets affected by decision maker’s age. Old adults are more likely to use heuristics and biases than young adults. Age related changes in decision making seems to get affected by the environment in which decision is made, personal relevance of a decision and experience with the decision domain.

Traditional theory of finance states that investor’s make decisions rationally and always follow sound logics while taking a decision. But behavioral scientist proclaims that decisions are made using thumb rules and shortcuts. There is no rational thinking guiding an individual’s decision

making process. Investor's gets swayed by their moods, emotions and past experiences. Hence their choices are an outcome of irrational investment decisions. With respect to age it is believed that increasing age leads to a shift in individual's basis of decision making from optimization to satisfaction. Growing by age people tend to rely on their experiences and prefer making a familiar choice rather than exploring new opportunities. There are many such aspects related to age and decision making. Therefore the present study aims to bring out neurobiological and behavioral changes associated with age of an individual in context to investment decision making.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Yoo (1994) identified a non linear relationship between portfolio allocation and aging of an individual. A cross sectional study was conducted using time series analysis. The findings of the study suggests that young as well as retired individuals prefers less risky investment options as compared to middle aged individuals. Individuals from different age group have different priorities when they determine their portfolio composition.

Korniotis and Kumar (2011) studied investment decisions of older individual investors. Outcome of the study suggests that "older and more experienced investors hold less risky portfolios, exhibit stronger preference for diversification, trade less frequently, exhibits a greater propensity for year-end tax loss selling, and exhibit weaker behavioral biases. Thus, their choices reflect greater knowledge about investing." Older investors are worst in applying investment knowledge and possess worst investment skills. The adverse effect of aging dominates positive effect of experience in case of investment decisions.

Mont (2011) focused on analyzing investment decisions made by young and old investors. The outcome of the research suggest that older investors display a variability in nucleus accumbens activity because of which they tend to make irrational and bold decisions. Older investors showed similar willingness as young investors to invest in stock. But their approach to decision making was distracted and rash. Because of which they many times ended up making a bad decision. Young investors seem to take more cautious decisions as they have to pay off debt and plan future.

Charles and Kasilingam (2013) analyzed how investor's age determines his investment behavior. They analyzed various demographic biases. Impact of these demographic variables was studied with respect to behavioral biases that later on effect the financial decisions. To analyze they considered 742 individual investors that invest or trade on Indian stock market. Cross tabulation and correspondence analysis was used to analyze the collected data. Statistical software SPSS was used to apply statistical tools. The study concluded that age is the most influential factor amongst all other factors that has a bearing on investment decisions of individual investors.

Onsomu (2015) studied the effect of age on investor decisions at the Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. There were four age brackets considered for the study 18-30, 31-40, 41-50 and above 50 years. The outcome of the study suggests that there exists a significant relationship between age and overconfidence bias. Investors within age group 18-30 years were most affected while investors in 31-40 age group was least impacted. Representative, confirmation and disposition bias was displayed by investors across all age brackets.

Gamble et.al (2015) used panel data of elderly individuals with an average age of 82 years. The objective of the study is to analyze the effect of declining cognition on financial decision making. The study concluded that declining cognition is associated with significant decline in financial literacy. Elderly were found to take help for their finances mainly from their spouse. Despite of declining cognition elderly were found to have confidence in their financial knowledge and management of finances.

Khoo (2016) claims that people in same age group tend to share certain circumstances in life owing to which some correlation was found between age of investors and their investment strategies. Young people have more risk taking capacity as they have more time to recover their losses if any. The earning power of older people is generally more as compared to young people and hence their starting capital is also high. Commitment and number of dependents tend to grow as one get older, hence older will take less risky decisions. But in reality there exist exceptions to these rules. If an individual belongs to a wealthy family or has made fortune at young age then his investment strategy may be different. Lastly it also depends on individuals preferences.

Shashikant (2019) identified that people find information load tiring as they age. One's ability to associate specific information with specific people, product or processes deteriorates with age. Therefore it is difficult for older people to filter information, handle complex product feature and shift their objective. Elders were found to go by generic names and specific brands. Their decisions are based on familiarity and past experience. The article further highlights various ways in which help can be extended to elderly in their decision making process.

Cannivet (2019) tried to identify what is the prime age group of an investor. Outcomes of many researches were discussed in his article. After analyzing it was concluded that older investors also follow the rules of investment but the effectiveness declines as one ages because of decrease in cognitive ability. Mostly people have an investing blind spot after the age of 60 which leads to poor financial decisions.

According to Edelman Financial Engine the previous researches that claims that older people cannot process much information due to decline in their cognitive ability is not necessarily true. The article cite outcome of a new study conducted at University of California and states that the financial expertise as well as knowledge that you gain in your lifetime offsets that natural decline in your cognitive ability. They also conclude that crystallized brain that is developed through knowledge & experience is more important in finance decision making than fluid brain which relates to logical thinking & information processing.

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES

3.1 Objective of the study

- 1) To segment individual investors on the basis of their demographic attributes.
- 2) To analyze the impact of age on investor's investment decisions.

3.2 Hypotheses

- 1) H1.1 There is no significant difference in size of investment portfolio of investors belonging to different age groups.

- 2) H1.2 There is no significant difference in return expectation between investors belonging to different age groups.
- 3) H1.3 There is no significant difference in investment objective of investors belonging to different age groups.
- 4) H1.4 There is no significant difference in frequency of portfolio revision of investors belonging to different age groups.
- 5) H1.5 There is no significant difference in risk preference of investors belonging to different age groups.
- 6) H1.6 There is no significant difference between investors belonging to different age groups in their preference of investment avenues.

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

The purpose of the research is both exploratory and descriptive. The study identifies demographic profile of investors. It is exploratory as it compares various groups of individuals divided on the basis of their age. It is also descriptive as it attempts to identify investment decision making process of investors.

3.4 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The universe for the present study comprises of all individual investors, while the target population will include all individual investors in India. Sampling unit can be defined as individuals who invest their savings in financial market. Individuals can be male or female, employed across any occupation category, and might have attended any level of education. With regards to age the sampling unit defines an age limit of above 18 years.

3.5 SAMPLE DESIGN

As the population was too large and heterogeneous Non – Probabilistic Sampling technique was used. The methods used to identify appropriate samples were Judgmental and Convenience sampling methods.

3.6 SAMPLE SIZE

The total number of questionnaires distributed was 1000. 558 questionnaires were received. From 558 questionnaires received, 545 fully responded questionnaires were identified. Thus the response rate was 55.8%.

3.7 TOOL FOR DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected using a self administered questionnaire. The first section of the questionnaire recorded variables like age, gender, education, occupation, yearly income.

The second section of questionnaire included questions related to financial decision of an individual. Most of the variables are measured using a close-ended multiple choice format

3.8 DATA ANALYSIS

Collected data is analyzed using statistical tools and are presented using tables and graphs. The analysis is carried out using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 for

Windows. The data analysis methods used were descriptive statistics, cross tabulation, bar charts, Chi-Square test, Kruskal Wallis test and Mann Whitney test.

4. Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

Demographic detail of respondents was summarized to analyze the basic features of sample chosen for study. The descriptive statistics comprises of list of variables considered and sample distribution across all the variables. As can be seen from table 1 that the sample includes 326 males and 219 females. Majority of respondents belong to 26-35 and 36-45 age groups. Percentage distribution of sample as per their educational qualification was found to be 4.8% with H.Sc as their education background, 25.7% are graduate, 41.8% are post graduate and 27.7% are professionals. Hence it can be said that majority respondents have above graduation level of education. Similarly distribution based on occupation shows that 48.6% belong to service class followed by business class (23.7%) and professionals (21.3%). Income distribution shows that 24.6% respondents have annual income less than 5 lakhs, 32.7% belongs to 5 lakhs to 10 lakhs income group, 26.4% belongs to 10 lakhs to 15 lakhs income group and 16.3% belong to income group above 15 lakhs.

Table 1: Demographic and Geographic Characteristics of the Sample

		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	326	59.8	59.8
	Female	219	40.2	100.0
	Total	545	100.0	100.0
Age (in years)	18-25	79	14.5	14.5
	26-35	244	44.8	59.3
	36-45	159	29.2	88.4
	Above 45	63	11.6	100.0
	Total	545	100.0	100.0
Education	H.SC	26	4.8	4.8
	Graduate	140	25.7	30.5
	Post Graduate	228	41.8	72.3
	Professional	151	27.7	100.0
	Total	545	100.0	100.0
Occupation	Service	265	48.6	48.6
	Business	129	23.7	72.3
	Housewife	35	6.4	78.7
	Professional	116	21.3	100
	Total	545	100	100
Yearly Income	Less than 5 lakhs	134	24.6	24.6
	5 lakhs to 10 lakhs	178	32.7	57.2
	10 lakhs to 15 lakhs	144	26.4	83.7
	Above 15 lakhs	89	16.3	100
	Total	100	100	100

4.2 Hypothesis Testing

The hypotheses of the study were analyzed using various statistical tools like chi square test, and Kruskal Wallis test. These tests were applied to various hypotheses depending upon the measurement scale of the variables.

H_{1.1} There is no significant difference in size of investment portfolio between investors of different age group.

Table 2: Investment Portfolio * Age Group Cross Tabulation

Investment Portfolio	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	Total
0 – Rs 50000	28	54	22	11	115
Rs 50000 – Rs 100000	17	43	14	7	81
Rs 100000 – Rs 500000	20	77	57	24	178
Rs 500000 – Rs 1000000	9	51	41	10	111
Above Rs 1000000	5	19	25	11	60
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 3: Chi-Square Test Investment Portfolio * Age

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	44.029	12	0.000*
Likelihood Ratio	44.48	12	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	26.62	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	545		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 6.94.

*Differences are significant at 1%

Outcome of cross tabulation between investment portfolio size and age of investors reveals that investors with portfolio size between 18 to 25 years of age have low investments while investors in 26 to 45 years age brackets display high amount of investment. Above 45 years of age portfolio size is generally in middle range.

Chi Square test was applied to identify relationship between age and portfolio size of investors.

The outcome of the study suggests that null hypothesis was rejected at 1% level of significance (Table 3). Thus it can be said that there exists a difference between portfolio size of investors across different age brackets.

H_{1.2} There is no significant difference in return expectation between investors of different age group.

Table 4: Expected Return * Age Group Cross Tabulation

Expected Return	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	Total
Up to 10%	39	85	46	22	192
11% to 15%	19	89	59	20	187
16% to 20%	15	48	42	13	118
Above 20%	6	22	12	8	48
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 5: Chi-Square Test Expected Return * Age Group

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	13.436	9	0.044*
Likelihood Ratio	13.129	9	0.157
Linear-by-Linear Association	3.741	1	0.053
N of Valid Cases	545		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 5.55.

*Differences are significant at 5%

It can be observed from the cross tabulation table that investors belonging to below 35 years and above 45 years of age category display high expected returns. While investors in age bracket 36 to 45 years have comparatively high expectation.

Influence of age over return expectation was tested using chi-square test. The result of the test revealed the statistics value as .044 which is less than .05. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected in this case. This indicates existence of an association between these two variables.

H_{1.3} There is no significant difference in investment objective of investors of different age group.

Table 6: Mean Rank Investment Objective * Age

Investment Objective	Age (in years)	N	Mean Rank
Capital Appreciation	18-25	79	298.72
	26-35	244	253.77
	36-45	159	279.92
	Above 45	63	297.76
	Total	545	
Regular Income	18-25	79	276.46
	26-35	244	276.88
	36-45	159	277.38
	Above 45	63	242.56
	Total	545	
Future Security	18-25	79	254.51
	26-35	244	273.45
	36-45	159	267.14
	Above 45	63	309.24

	Total	545	
Tax Benefit	18-25	79	260.75
	26-35	244	288.44
	36-45	159	265.92
	Above 45	63	246.43
	Total	545	
Status Quo	18-25	79	265.33
	26-35	244	273.83
	36-45	159	274.38
	Above 45	63	275.91
	Total	545	

Lower the mean, higher the preference

Table 7: Kruskal Wallis Test Investment Objective * Age

Investment Objectives	Capital Appreciation	Regular Income	Future Security	Tax Benefit	Status Quo
Chi-Square	8.03	2.78	4.852	5.19	0.249
Df	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.045*	0.427*	0.183*	0.158*	0.969*

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Age (in years)

**Differences are significant at 5%*

Preference of investment objective of investors across different age category is observed using mean ranks as shown in table 6. Investors in age group 18 to 25 years give more preference to future security while investors in age bracket of 26 to 35 years gives priority to capital growth. 36 to 45 years of age group investors prefer tax benefit while above 45 years prefer regular income.

Investment objective as a dependent variable was tested against independent variable age by applying Kruskal Wallis test. The outcome of the test reveals only in case of capital growth null hypothesis was rejected. For all other objectives null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance.

H_{1.4} There is no significant difference in frequency of portfolio revision of investors of different age group.

Table 8: Portfolio Revision * Age Cross Tabulation

Portfolio Revision	Age (in years)				Total
	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	
Monthly	34	85	19	6	144
Quarterly	17	59	27	6	109
Half Yearly	11	48	27	8	94
Yearly	10	37	49	38	134
More than a year	7	15	37	5	64
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 9: Chi Square test Portfolio Revision * Age

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	8.741a	12	0.025*
Likelihood Ratio	8.833	12	0.717
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.459	1	0.498
N of Valid Cases	545		

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 7.40.

*Differences are significant at 5%

Frequency of portfolio revision was cross tabulated across different age groups. It was observed that Young investors in the age bracket of 18-25 years and 26-35 years usually revised their portfolios more frequently than investors above 35 years. Young investors mostly revised every month and investors above 35 years mostly revised every year (Table 8).

Impact of age on frequency of portfolio revision was identified using chi square analysis. The P value of .025 shows that null hypothesis was rejected at 5% level of significance indicating no impact of age of investor on frequency of portfolio revision (Table 9).

H_{1.5} There is no significant difference in risk preference of investors of different age group.

Table 10: Risk Preference * Age Group Cross Tabulation

Risk Preference	18-25	26-35	36-45	Above 45	Total
No risk at all	6	8	5	5	24
Below average risk	22	19	48	37	126
Average risk	25	87	84	11	207
Above average risk	18	105	13	5	141
Very high risk	8	25	9	5	47
Total	79	244	159	63	545

Table 11: Chi-Square Test Risk Preference * Age Group

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square (a)	11.723	12	0.046*
Likelihood Ratio	11.387	12	0.496
Linear-by-Linear Association	0.01	1	0.919
N of Valid Cases	545		

*Differences are significant at 5%

Risk appetite of investors was understood by asking them to choose the risk preference they generally keep in mind before choosing a financial instrument. On classifying risk preference along with age of investors it was found that investors in age bracket of 18-25 years and 36-45 years were found to either prefer average risk or below average risk. Risk appetite of investors in age group 26-35 years was high in comparison to other age groups. They preferred above average risk or average risk. Investors above 45 years of age were reported to opt for low risk investment options

Chi square test statistics was used to assess the influence of age on risk appetite of investors. A calculated statistics value 0.046 reveals that the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level of significance and also verify the existence of an association between risk preference of investors and their age.

H_{1.6} There is no significant difference among investors of different age group in their preference of investment avenues

Table 12: Mean Ranks Investment Avenues * Age

	Age (in years)	N	Mean Rank
Bank Fixed Deposit and Other Government Securities	18-25	79	247.63
	26-35	244	275.6
	36-45	159	276.38
	Above 45	63	266.67
	Total	545	
Bonds and Debentures	18-25	79	264.94
	26-35	244	273.83
	36-45	159	276.36
	Above 45	63	271.4
	Total	545	
Equity	18-25	79	276.83
	26-35	244	273.2
	36-45	159	271.14
	Above 45	63	272.14
	Total	545	
Mutual Funds	18-25	79	280.68
	26-35	244	260.83
	36-45	159	258.42
	Above 45	63	276.48
	Total	545	
Derivatives	18-25	79	288.1
	26-35	244	281.65
	36-45	159	282.8
	Above 45	63	286.23
	Total	545	

Lower the mean, higher the preference

Table 13: Kruskal Wallis Test Investment Avenue * Age

	Bank Fixed Deposit and Other Government Securities	Bonds and Debentures	Equity	Mutual Funds	Derivatives
Chi-Square	2.781	0.306	0.077	2.515	3.369
Df	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	0.027*	0.959*	0.994*	0.473*	0.338*

a. Kruskal Wallis Test

b. Grouping Variable: Age (in years)

**Differences are significant at 5%*

Investor's preference was recorded by taking ranks for five investment avenues. The mean of ranks was then calculated and classified across different age category. It can be seen from the rank allotted that young investors belonging to age group 18-25 years and above 45 years preferred bank fixed deposit and other government securities as they might be willing to take less risk. Investors in other two age groups of 26-35 years and 36-45 years preferred mutual funds

In order to examine influence of age on investment avenue choice of investor kruskal Wallis test was applied. The outcome of the test shows that null hypothesis is accepted in all cases except for bank fixed deposits and other government securities. Null hypothesis was rejected at 5% level of significance in case of bank fixed deposits and other government securities. This signifies that no difference in choice of investment avenues with respect to age was found for other avenues.

5. CONCLUSION

Age dependent behavior in your financial decision has many useful implications and therefore it has been long studied by many researchers. The outcome of the present study is in line with the previous researches that states that age influence overall financial decision of an individual. Although now a days there is no age bar as far as information availability is concerned but still the ability to process this information vary across age groups.

From the analysis of findings of the study it can be suggested that in the early years of investing that is in 20s and 30s one should focus aggressively on growth, should take active part in investment decisions and aim to take maximum benefit of compounding. At the age of starting 40s one reaches peak earning time, therefore it's the best time to balance your investments between growth and steadier investment options. Your investment choice in 50s must match with your retirement goals, income levels, tax liability and projected retirement income. Your age determines and influence many important areas of day to day and long term decision making. Therefore it must be consciously considered when taking investment decisions.

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